

Ear tag deployed accelerometer successfully infers sheep behaviour

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Abstract

A study was conducted to determine the viability of ear tag deployed accelerometers to infer behaviours related to grazing and pasture height in sheep. Nine ryegrass/white clover pasture plots were mown to three different heights: “Low” (2.5 cm), “Medium” (5 cm) and “High” (10 cm). Sheep were allocated to one of three groups with each group grazing each height treatment for 36 hours over one week. Accelerometer signals were annotated against video recordings. Behaviours isolated from video analysis included: standing, walking, ruminating and grazing. Head up and head down posture was successfully inferred from the accelerometer signals by monitoring the raw Y- and Z-axes. Sheep grazing the “High” treatment tended to graze more consistently than sheep grazing the “Low” treatment which grazed sporadically as they had to search for food. Based on movement intensity (signal vector magnitude), differences ($P < 0.05$) between grazing “Low” and “High” treatments were found in the number of counts above a threshold of 1.4. It was concluded that an ear attached tri-axial accelerometer could identify behaviours that were relevant to grazing and also determine when sheep were grazing either low or high pasture.

Background

Profitable livestock production from forages depends largely on the quantity and quality of the forage, and the animal’s ability to harvest that forage. Monitoring these three variables has traditionally been a hands-on, optical task that is both time and labour demanding. Correlating animal behaviour with favourable or detrimental environmental impacts allows for optimum intervention strategies to be employed at the correct time for peak impact (Handcock et al., 2009).

Remote monitoring is less time consuming, while providing a higher level of diagnostic accuracy than conventional livestock monitoring methods (Robert et al., 2009). An accelerometer is a device that measures acceleration forces of both static and dynamic movement (Andrejašić, 2008). This information can then be used to determine body positioning, posture and motion detection (Ravi, 2005). Accelerometers have been used to detect different animal behaviours such as feeding, ruminating and walking, as well as how these behaviours change when the animal is exposed to different stimuli and conditions (Alvarenga et al., 2016; Andrews et al., 2015; Ravi, 2005; Robert et al., 2009). The vast majority of studies that have been undertaken using accelerometers to detect behaviours have used body or collar deployments.

Ear mounted technology such as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags have proven to be the optimum placement because of the ease of deployment, access and the miniaturisation of the hardware allowing for minimal effect on the animal. However, the ear is an appendage that undergoes sporadic movement when the animal is in motion, making behaviour sensing more difficult. As such, deploying sensors in an ear tag form factor on sheep has previously been avoided. Ear tag deployed accelerometers have successfully identified sheep behaviours such as walking, standing and grazing (Barwick 2017). However, there is limited information on how ear tag deployed accelerometers can identify feeding behaviours related to pasture height.

The aim of this current study was to determine if an ear tag deployed accelerometer could infer aspects of sheep feeding behaviour during grazing of three sward heights: “Low”, “Medium” and “High”.

Methods

This study was approved by the University of New England Animal Ethics Committee and followed the University of New England's code of conduct for research in meeting the Australian Code of Practice for the Care and Use of animals (AEC 15-132).

Study design

The study period was between 7th and 13th February 2016, inclusive. Nine plots 48 m x 1.2 m were constructed from 70% ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) and 30% white clover (*Trifolium repens* cv. Trophy). Each plot was prepared three days before the study began using a mower (Honda HRU 197 4-stroke lawnmower, Honda Australia) calibrated to create pasture height treatments of either "Low" (2.5 cm; ~400 kg DM/ha), "Medium" (5 cm; ~900 kg DM/ha) or "High" (10 cm; ~1200 kg DM/ha). Pre- and post-grazing biomass was estimated using the median quadrat technique and a GreenSeeker™ (Trimble Inc.) active optical sensor. Each height treatment was replicated three times.

Nine, 4-year old, dry Merino ewes weighing approximately 60 kg were randomly assigned to one of the three pasture height treatment groups and would remain in that group for the duration of the study. Each group of three sheep grazed each pasture height treatment for 36 hours, starting at 1800 h and finishing at 0600 h the day after. At the end of each grazing session the sheep were run as one group grazing pasture (~900 kg DM/ha) for 12 hours (rest period) between recordings in a holding paddock to level out their stomach contents.

Accelerometers

Axivity AX3 (Axivity, Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom) accelerometers (23 x 32.5 x 7.6 mm; 11 g) were used. The AX3 is a combination logging sensor that records acceleration (*g*) along three axes (*X*, *Y* and *Z*), is waterproof and is able to be used under a wide range of environmental conditions. For this current study, acceleration signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 12.5 Hz (12.5 samples per second) and stored on the internal 512 MB NAND flash memory. The AX3 was attached to a trimmed, standard ear-tag (Allflex Australia Pty Ltd., Capalaba, Qld) using adhesive and clear shrink wrap. It was then attached to the right ear of each sheep. The orientation of the accelerometer was such that the *X*-axis indicated up (+ve) and down (-ve), the *Y*-axis indicated left (+ve) and right (-ve) and the *Z*-axis indicated forward (+ve) and back (-ve) movements. The ear tag was removed at the end of each session to retrieve data.

Observations

Sheep exhibiting grazing, ruminating, walking and standing behaviours were recorded with a video camera (JVC Everio GZ-R10, JVC Kenwood, Malaysia) four times daily (0800, 1100, 1400 and 1800 h) for 2 h each. Behaviours were classified according to Alvarenga et al. (2016).

Differences between sward heights

The summary metric used in this current study was the Signal Vector Magnitude (SVM; equation 1; Zhang and Sawchuk 2011). The SVM feature is independent of orientation and measures the instantaneous intensity of movements at time (*t*).

$$SVM(t) = \sqrt{a_x(t)^2 + a_y(t)^2 + a_z(t)^2} \quad (1)$$

where $a_x(t)$, $a_y(t)$ and $a_z(t)$ are the values of the *X*, *Y* and *Z* axes signals at time, *t*, respectively.

Twenty five, 120 s epoch replicates of standing, walking, grazing and ruminating behaviours were isolated from sheep grazing "Low" and "High" sward height treatments. Six thresholds (0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.6) were tested to determine the differences between the two treatment heights grazing patterns. The threshold best suited to this data set was a magnitude of 1.4.

Statistical analysis

Differences in grazing behaviour between pasture height treatments "Low" and "High", the counts above a threshold of 1.4 were analysed using a two-sample *t*-test (Cressie & Whitford, 1986).

Results

Two Axivity sensors malfunctioned during the first session and were replaced. Data from these two were not used in the analysis.

Inferring posture related sheep behaviour

Standing, walking, grazing and ruminating behaviours were successfully identified from accelerometer signals. There was a small average acceleration range of ~0.04 g when the sheep was standing. The average acceleration range gradually increases from 0.4 g to 2.5 g as the sheep walks and then moves into a run. Ruminating was identified by the repetitive chew, swallow and regurgitate, chew pattern. The increase in amplitude was not confused with feeding as the Z-axis crosses the Y-axis indicating that the head is raised while when the Y-axis was above the Z-axis the head was lowered (see Figure 1). Grazing behaviour showed a consistent acceleration range of ~1.0 g for all axes.

Figure 1. Posture as determined from raw accelerometer signals for sheep grazing
A. “High” sward height treatment **B. “Low” sward height treatment.**

Differences between sward heights

Sheep grazing the “High” sward height treatment tended to graze more consistently whereas sheep grazing the “Low” treatment tended to graze more sporadically. Figure 2 illustrates the box plot when counts of SVM were greater than the threshold of 1.4 for sheep 3. Overall, there were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher number of counts greater than 1.4 when sheep grazed “High” than for “Low”.

Figure 2. Box plot of number of times the threshold of 1.4 was exceeded for “High” and “Low” treatment heights for sheep 3. Mean count for “High” is 68.9 and for “Low” is 34.1.

Discussion

The current study used sheep with ear tag deployed accelerometers to isolate behaviour when they grazed pastures of three different sward heights. Accelerometers have successfully isolated particular sheep behaviours such as standing, lying, walking, ruminating, grazing and running (Alvarenga et al. 2016; Dobos et al. 2016; Marais et al. 2014).

In our current study, deployment of an accelerometer on an ear tag was able to successfully isolate standing, walking, ruminating and grazing behaviours when sheep grazed different sward height treatments. Sheep posture, as determined by head up/down, was also determined from ear tag deployed accelerometers. Differences ($P < 0.05$) were found between sward heights designated as “High” (10 cm) and “Low” (2.5 cm) when SVM exceeded a threshold of 1.4. Sheep posture was isolated from raw accelerometer Y- and Z-axes that indicated when the head was either down (grazing) or up (not grazing). Previous studies have shown that accelerometers are able to successfully identify head up/down posture (Alvarenga et al., 2016). They showed that grazing behaviour could be separated from other behaviours using the log of the mean of the X-axis over three different epoch lengths. In their study, the accelerometer was attached to the under-side of a halter. In this current study, the ear tag deployed accelerometer was able to successfully determine posture changes when the head was either up or down.

Further research is required to develop algorithms suitable to calculate time spent grazing. Also, how the use of ear tag deployed accelerometers can be used to improve producer decision making requires further study. Linking this methodology with suitable telemetry technology will require further study.

Conclusion

This current study confirmed that ear tag deployed accelerometers on sheep are capable of isolating behaviours when sheep graze different sward height treatments. Further research is required to develop algorithms that can be used to remotely identify sheep behaviour, especially grazing. This will enable the time spent grazing to be calculated and improve decision making for producers when allocating paddocks for grazing, including supplementary feeding strategies.

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